

TAKRA VARIETIES, PROPERTIES, GUNAS AND IMPORTANCE OF TAKRPANA IN UDARA ROGA

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Article Received on 05 Dec. 2025,
Article Revised on 25 Dec. 2025,
Article Published on 01 Jan. 2026

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18093691>

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How to cite this Article: Pooja Devi*, Roopam Bhardwaj*, Prof. Navneet Kumar Sharma**. (2026) TAKRA VARIETIES, PROPERTIES, GUNAS AND IMPORTANCE OF TAKRPANA IN UDARA ROGA. World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research, 15(1), 394-402.

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ABSTRACT

Takra is a widely used Ayurvedic dietary formulation known for its **agni deepana** and **Tridosha Shamaka** properties. Classical texts like Charaka Samhita, Susruta samhita and Ashtanga Hridaya highlight its role in managing various gastrointestinal disorders, particularly Udara Roga. Takra acts as a natural Probiotic, promoting gut health, improving digestion, and removing Ama. Different types of Takra preparations, based on fat content and doshic condition, are indicated for specific subtypes of Udara Roga. This paper reviews the therapeutic utility, types, properties, and clinical applications of Takra, emphasizing its importance as both a dietary and medicinal agent in Ayurvedic management of digestive disorders. **Aim:** To explore the varieties, properties, therapeutic uses and clinical significance of Takra (buttermilk) with special reference to its role in the management of Udara Roga (abdominal disorders). **Objective:** To evaluate the pharmacological and therapeutic properties (Guna, Veerya,

Vipaka) of different types of Takra. To assess the effectiveness of Takrapana in gastrointestinal diseases, especially Udara Roga. To establish Takra as a ayurvedic Probiotic and dietary recommendation in udara roga. **Materials and Methods:** Data was collected from classical Ayurvedic texts like Charaka Samhita, Sushruta Samhita, Ashtanga Hridaya, Bhavprakasha and various research articles and journals. Different types of Takra

preparations and their usage were documented. **Results:** Takra possesses Agni Deepana, Tridosha Shamaka, Srotoshodhana, and Grahi properties. Its administration helps in enhancing digestion, reducing Ama, balancing Tridosha, and managing Udara Roga effectively. Different types of Takra combinations are indicated for various subtypes of Udara roga (Vatodara, Pittodara, Kaphodara, etc.). **Conclusion:** Takra, when used as Takrapana with appropriate ingredients and as per the Dosha condition, plays a vital role in correcting Agnimandhya and managing Udara Roga. It serves as an Ayurvedic Probiotic that strengthens gut immunity and supports gastrointestinal health. Daily inclusion of Takra is beneficial for all types of body constitution (Prakriti).

INTRODUCTION

Samhithas like Sushruta samhita, Charaka samhita and Ashtanga hridaya of Ayurveda describes the advantages of Takra in gastrointestinal disorders like Grahani, Udara, Arsha etc. According to Ayurveda, the intestinal disorders are caused due to the diminished agni. Takra, like Ahara, is advantageous for both healthy people and those who are ill (food). Aahara is similar to Prana (basis of life). The best medication, according to Acharya Kashyap, is Aahara. One of the Ahara Dravya identified in Ayurveda as having many therapeutic virtues is Takra (buttermilk). Takra is recommended for a variety of illnesses, including Grahani (sprue), piles, diarrhea, etc. as a single medication, Anupan (vehicle), or Pathya (wholesome). Ayurveda emphasizes the significance of Agni (digestive fire) in maintaining the body's health.

It provides multiple health benefits such as it decreases edema, controls diarrhoea, anemia, hemorrhoids, stimulates digestive fire. Ayurveda, explains three types of buttermilk with their properties based on fat content such as fat-free, half fat and full fat which are to be consumed according to the Agni. Probiotics are called "good" or "helpful" bacterias as they help keep our gut healthy. Takra as a probiotics contains several important vitamins and minerals, such as vitamin B12, riboflavin, calcium and phosphorus and is also low in fat and calories.^[1]

Ayurveda emphasizes the significance of Agni (digestive fire) in maintaining the body's health. If disrupted, Agni can lead to the above-mentioned illnesses. It is intriguing to see how Takra serves as the principal digestive help in ailments connected to the Agni. Takra can also be utilized as a Pathya Ahara, or a healthy diet, to keep the body in good condition.^[2]

Probiotics stimulate the production of antibodies, enhance the systemic activity of macrophages and increase the number of killer cells hence probiotics have the immunomodulator effect in the human body thus improving the immune system. In addition, probiotics relieves constipation by regulating bowel movements, improves energy levels by enhancing B-complex synthesis, protects the vital organs like heart, kidney, lungs and liver with its antioxidant properties. Probiotics supports the immune system to battle infection, protects the urinary tract from infection, helps to heal peptic ulcer and prevents diarrhoea, gastroenteritis and other bowel problems. Takra (buttermilk) is one among them which is grouped under gorasa varga (milk and milk products).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Material collected from charka samhita, Sushruta samhita, Ashtanga hridaya, Bhava prakasha, research publications etc.

Results - Takra is also found in Vedas where it is mentioned that God got immortality due to apious drink (Amrut) in heaven and the humans have Takra (buttermilk) on The Earth. To be immortal in the heaven as quoted in Vaidyakiya Subhashit Sahityam.

Properties of Takra

It is of 2 types based on the taste – (rasa- Kashaya, amla, laghu, agnideepak, kapha vata nashak)

Rasa - Madhura and Amla (sweet and sour) with Kashaya anurasa (astringent in secondary taste);

Guna - Laghu (light), ruksha (dry)

Veerya - Ushna Veerya (hot in potency)

Vipaka - Madhura Vipaka (sweet at the end of digestion)

Doshkarma - Though it mainly acts on Kapha and Vata it is considered to pacify Tridosha. Even though buttermilk is considered to pacify Tridosha, it can be used with combination of different drugs to enhance its Doshas pacifying property.

Doshagnata: Tridosahara Karmukatas, Srotoshodhana, Agni Deepana, Avrushya, Balya, Grahi, Laghava, Tushtikara, Varnya, and Hridaya.^[3]

Table no. 1: Preparation of various types of Takra.^[4]

S.No.	Type of takra	Preparation	Property
1	Ghola	curds with its sara, churned with or without adding water.	Vata nashak and Pitta nashak after adding water
2	Mathita	curds without sara, churned without adding water the fat is separated and the curd is churned.	Kapha shamak and Pitta shamak
3	Takra	curds churned by adding water- 1/4th of the quantity of curds.	Agnideepaka, Viryavardhak, Truptikaraka and Vata nashak
4	Udavisht	curds churned by adding half the quantity of water.	Kaphakarak, Balavardhak and Aamnashak
5	Chachika	More water is added after the curd is mixed and the fat is removed.	Vata shamak, Kaphakarak

Gunas of takra**PROPERTIES OF TAKRA PREPARED BY DIFFERENT ANIMALS MILK**

1. Gavya Takra: Shrestha is a type of Takra made from cow's milk. It stimulates the Jatharaghi, gives relief to Arshas, Gulma, Atisara, Pleeha Roga, and Grahani Vikara, and has Medhya (memory power).
2. Mahisha Takra (Buffalow's Milk): Kaphavardhana and Shopha kara are performed with Takra made from buffalo milk by Sandra Guna and Guru.
3. Aja/Chhaga Takra: Aja/Chhaga Takra is a goat's milk preparation that is mentioned in the Gulma, Grahani, Arsha, Shotha, and Pandu Rogas. It is prepared with Snigdha, Laghu, and Tridosahara.^[5]

ASHTA GUNAS OF TAKRA

1. Kshut Vardhana—increases hunger.
2. Netra Rujapaha—treats eye conditions.
3. Pranadayaka - Pranada Pada.
4. Shonita (Rakta) kara
5. Mamsa Kara.
6. Amahara—Ama is relieved.
7. Abhighatahara—provides comfort throughout trauma.
8. Kaphahara Vata Hara^[6]

Table no. 2: Types of Takra based on fat content.^[7]

1	Ruksha Takra (butter is completely separated)	Used in the weakest parts of the body, Kapha prakopa, Mandagni, and Adhambala
2	Ardhodhrut Sneh (half of the butter is separated)	used for Madhyam Bala, Mandtar Agni, and Pittaprakop (moderate body strength)
3	Anudhrut Sneh (fat is not separated)	Used for Vataprakopa, Mandatama Agni and Utambala (Strong body strength)

Importance of Takrapana

Just like amrita to Suras Takra is for humans. Just like amrita to Suras Takra is for humans. Udasvit helps in mitigation of Ama, Chachika easily digestible, mitigates Pitta and Vata, and acts as Agnideepaka.

He who uses Takra daily does not suffer from diseases, and diseases cured by Takra do not re-occur. He who uses Takra daily does not suffer from diseases, and diseases cured by Takra do not re-occur. Amlatakra with Shunti and Saindhava- mitigates Vatadosha. Amlatakra with Sita- mitigates Pitta Dosha. Amlatakra with Vyosha and Kshara- mitigates Kapha Dosha.^[8]

Table no. 3: Takrapana according to Dosha.^[9]

Vatadosha.	Amla takra with Shunti and Saindhava
Pitta Dosha.	Madhura takra with Sita- mitigates
Kapha Dosha	Takra with Vyosha and Kshara- mitigates

Table no. 4: Takrapana according to Dosha.^[10]

Vataprakopa	Amla takra + Saindhava lavana
Pitta prakopa	Madhura takra + sarkra
Kapha prakopa	Trayusna + Yavkshara + Takra

Importance of Takra

The importance of Takra is mainly described by Charaka in Charaka samhita under various context. Charaka has indicated Takra in disorders such as Snehavyapad complication due to overuse of oily substances), Gara Visha (Low Potency Poison), Shotha Grahanidosha, Mutragraha (difficulty in Micturition), Udara, ascites, Aruchi (anorexia), in Udarroga chikitsa. Charak has also mentioned that Takra (buttermilk) can be used in Mandagni(Low Digestive Fire), Gaurava (heaviness in the body), Arochaka (anorexia), Atisara (diarrhea) and Vata -Kapha pradhana vyadhi.^[11] In Arsha (piles) Takra (buttermilk) is indicated in Vata –

Kapha pradhana Arsha. Takra (buttermilk) is also said as the best medicine for Vata -Kapha pradhana disorders.^[12]

According to Bhavprakasha Nighantu, a person who consumes Takra never gets sick, and when Takra (buttermilk) is used as medicine to treat a condition, there is never a relapse of that condition.

Takra reduces Kapha, Vata, and prevents Pitta from escalating. Takra performs the function of Tridoshshamaka as a result of these Gunas.

TAKRA SEVANA KALA

Depending upon the Rogi, Roga Bala and Ritu Anurasa, Takra must be administered for 7 days or 10 days or 15 days or a month. Thereafter, it should be gradually withdrawn inside the same quantity wherein it changed into extended within the beginning. While lowering the buttermilk, the affected person's total meals need not be decreased. Adaptation of this manner will promote and preserve the power of his digestive power.^[13]

INDICATIONS FOR TAKRA PANA

Agnimandhya condition, Sheeta Kala, and Marghavarodha condition, mainly indicated in kaphajaroga, vatavikrati. vyadhi like - Shopha, Arsha, Grahani Dosha, Mutra Graha, Udara, Aruchi, Pandu, Gara Visha, Pleeha Roga, Arochaka, Gulma and Ghrita Vyapatha.^[14]

Table no. 5: Takra Prayoga in Udara Roga Patients with Udara Roga benefit from Takra.^[15]

S.No.	Udara Roga	Takra preparation
1	Vatodara	Takra added with Pippali, Saindhava
2	Pittodara	Takra, which is Swadu and has Sita and Madhuka Churna, added to it.
3	Kaphodara	Yavani, Saindhava, Ajaji, Trikatu, and Madhu were added to Takra.
4	Nichayodara	Trayushana, Kshara, and Lavana were added to Takra.
5	Plihodara	Madhu, Taila, and the Churnas of Vacha, Shunti, Shatahva, Kustha, and Saindhava were added to Takra.
6	Udakodara	Trikatu Churna added with Takra
7	Baddhodara	Hapusha, Ajaji, Yavani, and Saindhava Lavana were added to Takra
8	Chidrodara	Pippali and Madhu added with Takra.

Table no. 6: Composition of Takra.^[16]

Nutritional value per 100 g

Energy	169 kJ (40 kcal)
Carbohydrates	4.8 g
Fat	0.9 g
Protein	3.3 g
Minerals	(12%)
Calcium	116 mg

CONTRAINDICATIONS FOR TAKRA PANA^[17]

Ushna Kala, Kshata, Durbala Purusha, Murcha, Bhrama, Daha and Rakta Pitta.

Assimilation

Water content in Takra at its highest is 91–92%. High water content allows the use of Takra both for maintaining the water balance of the human body and as a quick thirst quencher. As the water content of Takra is mainly bound to proteins, it is absorbed from the intestines slowly enough that this drink is better than any type of water, either ordinary or flavored.^[18]

DISCUSSION

The first line of treatment of Arshas is Vatanulomana and Agnibalavardhana. Takra by its Vata-pittahara guna brings down the pain presented in case of Arshas, by Swadupaka it mitigates the burning sensation, by Kashaya rasa it stops the bleeding, by its Deepana property cures Agni-mandya, thereby helping in SrotoShuddi. Based on Agnibala of the patient the suitable Takra with or without fat.

Takra (Buttermilk)- Deepana, Pachana, Sangrahi and Tridosahara. Laghu Guna and Deepana properties of Takra helped to correct the Agni Due to its Madhura Vipaka helped in the balance of Pitta. Also, its Vatahara property helped to correct the vitiated Samana Vayu.^[19] The Grahi action of Takra subsided Drava Mala Pravrutti which has been proved to restore the bacterial flora of the intestinal mucosa. Because of this unique combination takra can be included in daily diet for all type of Prakriti. Takra can also be utilized as a Pathya Ahara, or a healthy diet, to keep the body in good condition.

CONCLUSION

Takra is helpful in counteracting the aggravated Vata because of its Madhura (sweet), Amla (sour), and Sandra Guna (density) Rasa, while Madhura Vipaka is helpful in counteracting the aggravated Pitta because it neither aggravates nor alleviates Pitta, and because of its

Kashaya Rasa (astringent taste), Ushna Veerya (hot potency), Vikasitwat counteracting the aggravated kapha, which Takra acquires a variety of properties based on numerous kinds of preparations made possible by Samskara.^[20] Therefore, the Takra and Takra Kalpanas should be used to cure a variety of illnesses based on the Yukti of the Vaidya and dependent on Rogi and Roga Bala.

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